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Valuation of human capital by the private sector firms in the service industry in Sri Lanka

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the research was to investigate employee perceptions towards human capital valuation and reporting (HCVR) by the private sector firms belonging to the service industry. A random sample of 210 employees in managerial capacities of the firms that belong to the service industry responded to the self-administered questionnaire designed for the study. Analysis of the survey data was conducted using SPSS. It was found that respondents support the need for reporting human capital data in annual reports and agreed that it could have an impact on attracting and retaining employees. Further, employees have concerns over the transparency in reporting human capital value, as manipulations would ultimately erode and hinder the rationale for its emergence. Furthermore, findings showed that there are significant differences in perceptions towards HCVR by job level, gender, and tenure in the workplace of the respondents. Overall, the findings led to support for human capital valuation, though there are certain concerns over valuation itself.

Keywords: Human capital, Human capital valuation, Service industry.

1 INTRODUCTION

The recognition that much of the added value created by firms is becoming more dependent on assets other than physical capital has stimulated a vast literature in the area of intellectual capital and intangible assets (Berkowitz, 2001; Leadbeater, 2000; Mayo, 2001). In particular, emphasis has been placed on the importance of a firm's human capital- the value-creating skills, competencies, talents, and abilities of its workforce. Thus, human capital is something that employees bring to an organization (and take with them when they leave), yet is also something that is developed within the workplace through training and work experience (Akuratiyagamage, 2003; Miller and Wurzburg, 1995; Wickramasinghe, 2006). Thus, human capital in a real sense is an "invisible asset" (Itami, 1987). The only way to compete in today's knowledge economy is to fully exploit this resource. It is human capital, allied to effective leadership, that creates competitive advantage, both of organizations and of nations (Leadbeater, 2000).

The vast majority of literature on human capital proposes elaborate systems for measuring a firm's human assets. However, the studies that have been conducted to investigate employees' perceptions towards the adoption of human capital valuation and reporting (HCVR) in Sri Lanka are rare. In adopting a new practice, there is a need to investigate employee perceptions towards it. The preliminary investigations of the researcher revealed that the private sector firms belonging to the service industry would take the lead in adopting this practice since they mainly rely on human resources in creating a competitive advantage. Therefore, the purpose of the research was to investigate employee perceptions towards HCVR by the private sector firms belonging to the service industry in Sri Lanka.

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The issue of what contributes to competitive advantage has seen a shift in emphasis away from external positioning in the industry and relative balance of competitive forces, towards an acknowledgement that internal resources should be viewed as crucial to sustained organizational effectiveness (Wright et al, 2001). The work of Penrose (1959) represents the beginning of the resource-based view of the firm, later articulated by Rumelt (1984), Barney (1991, 1995), and Dierickx and Cool (1989).

Tight labor markets have emphasized the importance of a firm's ability to attract and retain highly qualified and motivated individuals. But imperfect knowledge of the value of those individuals still allows talent to ebb away because of poor decisions driven, for example, by short-term cost-cutting. This suggests that the short-term euphoria of cost-cutting is eventually followed by the sobering recognition that when "people" costs are cut, so too are the assets that generate future revenue and profitability. Therefore, this has raised the concept that people are no longer expendable in organizations and can no longer be treated as a source for cost-cutting. Hence, they are recognized as "assets" that can derive a competitive advantage in an era that is dominated by "knowledge". These default factors have laid the foundation stone for the ongoing popularity of HCVR, which means identifying and measuring the value of human resources and communicating the information to the interested parties (Boudreau and Ramstad, 1997; Cascio, 1991; Ferguson and Berger, 1985; Flamholtz, 1985). The concept of value has two different meanings. 'Value' expresses the utility of a particular resource (e.g., the future use of a capital asset) and the purchasing power of the resource (e.g., money, securities). If an object is not capable of rendering future economic services in the form of utility to the possessor, no value can be attached to it. Crucial need for HCVR

arises mostly in people-oriented knowledge-based organizations (Baron, 2003).

The currently accepted accounting principles and their related reporting requirements rest on the foundational assumption that physical assets (land, machinery, buildings, natural resources, and inventory) generate wealth. Human capital does not even appear in annual reports. Reporting on human capital is not easy. The human capital of an organization is its most valuable but also most volatile asset. It is highly mobile. Because it is too hard to measure, organizations cannot ignore it. There is overwhelming evidence – particularly from the UK, USA, and Singapore – that suggests that people working in a climate of high-performance people management practices are the key driver of competitive success (Baron, 2003). As a result, there have been calls for human assets to be incorporated into firms' financial reports, thereby giving investors a much clearer picture of where value lies (Flamholtz, 1985; Scarpello and Theeke, 1989).

Some of the reported benefits of human capital valuation include better assessment of business targets in the context of employee capabilities; the identification of skill gaps; improved management of acquisitions; better staff retention; and improved targeting of pay and reward costs. Though measuring approaches to human capital have been widely debated over the past 40 years since the concept was first popularized (Schultz, 1961), many professional associations worldwide engaged in a variety of activities concerned with improved reporting, internal measurement, and management of human capital (Baron, 2003). The initiatives on human capital reporting call for more information to be included in firms' financial reports. However, according to researchers, human capital is poorly understood, inadequately identified, inefficiently managed, and inconsistently reported (Baron, 2003).

3 METHODOLOGY

For the investigation, a random sample of respondents was drawn to be enabled to extrapolate any subsequent findings. The self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the main mode for data collection. The questionnaire was distributed to 50 randomly selected organizations belonging to the service industry (such as banking, IT, and management consultancy). 10 questionnaires were distributed to each company, requesting any graduate employee in any management capacity to fill out. The final sample of the study consisted of 210 randomly selected respondents, resulting in a 42 per cent response rate. With regard to characteristics of the sample, 41 per cent were female while 59 per cent was male. 39 per cent belonged to the junior management level, 43 per cent belonged to the middle management level, and 18 per cent belonged to the top management level. With regard to the number of years of service in the organization, 15 per cent had over 10 years of service, 41 per cent had 5 to 10 years of service, and 44 per cent had less than 5 years of service. Analysis of the survey data was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences.

4 RESULTS

The results of the perceptions towards HCVR are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Perceptions towards HCVR

	Mean
Awareness of the concept of HCVR	3.71
HC should be valued and reported	4.64
HC should be considered as an asset	2.18
Firms should make arrangements to value HC	3.84
Firms should make arrangements to report HCV information in annual reports	2.24
HC reporting will influence a firm's capability to attract and retain employees	4.14
HCVR will enhance job satisfaction	4.04
HCVR will enhance career satisfaction	4.19
HCVR will create transparency	3.52
HCVR will create a standard	3.59
HCVR will create a competitive advantage	3.64
HCVR will hinder interpersonal relationships	3.11

The results of the t-test that show differences in the perceptions towards HCVR by gender are shown in Table 2. The analysis showed significant differences in 4 items. For the item "Firms should make arrangements to report HCV information in annual reports," females scored higher and significantly different from males. For the rest of the three items, males scored higher and significantly different from females.

Table 2: Perceptions towards HCVR by Gender

	G	Mean	t	Sig.
Awareness of the concept of HCVR	F	3.63	-1.03	.302
	M	3.75		
HC should be valued and reported	F	4.56	-1.73	.085*
	M	4.70		
HC should be considered as an asset	F	2.13	-.74	.455
	M	2.20		
Firms should make arrangements to value HC	F	3.83	-.06	.950
	M	3.84		
Firms should make arrangements to report HCV information in annual reports	F	2.48	2.23	.026*
	M	2.06		
HC reporting will influence a firm's capability to attract and retain employees	F	3.93	-1.33	.184
	M	4.12		
HCVR will enhance job satisfaction	F	3.89	-2.07	.039*
	M	4.14		
HCVR will enhance career satisfaction	F	4.23	.65	.512
	M	4.16		
HCVR will create transparency	F	3.58	.823	.411
	M	3.47		
HCVR will create a standard	F	3.46	-1.88	.061*
	M	3.68		
HCVR will create a competitive advantage	F	3.62	-.19	.849
	M	3.65		
HCVR will hinder interpersonal relationships	F	3.00	-.50	.618
	M	3.16		

Notes: * p<0.05, G=Gender; F=Female (N=86), M=Male (N=124).

The results of ANOVA for the differences in the perceptions towards HCVR by job level are shown in Table 3. The analysis showed significant differences in perceptions in 9 items. A Bonferroni test was conducted to identify the differences. It was found that for two items, “Firms should make arrangements to value HC” and “HCVR will create transparency,” top management scored higher and significantly different from the other two categories. For the rest of the seven items, junior management scored lower and significantly different from the other two categories.

Table 3: Perceptions towards HCVR by Job Level

	JL	Mean	F	Sig.
Awareness of the concept of HCVR	J	3.21	27.23	.000***
	M	3.92		
	T	4.23		
HC should be valued and reported	J	4.65	.83	.438
	M	4.60		
	T	4.73		
HC should be considered as an asset	J	2.11	2.50	.084
	M	2.15		
	T	2.39		
Firms should make arrangements to value HC	J	3.41	13.65	.000***
	M	3.85		
	T	4.79		
Firms should make arrangements to report HCV information in annual reports	J	2.10	7.12	.001**
	M	2.48		
	T	2.52		
HCVR will influence a firm’s capability to attract and retain employees	J	3.46	30.84	.000***
	M	4.35		
	T	4.53		
HCVR will enhance job satisfaction	J	3.68	17.41	.000***
	M	4.14		
	T	4.58		
HCVR will enhance career satisfaction	J	3.89	12.70	.000***
	M	4.31		
	T	4.55		
HCVR will create transparency	J	3.33	8.97	.000***
	M	3.46		
	T	4.05		
HCVR will create a standard	J	3.32	9.92	.000***
	M	3.67		
	T	4.00		
HCVR will create a competitive advantage	J	3.01	44.65	.000***
	M	4.02		
	T	4.08		
HCVR will hinder interpersonal relationships	J	3.00	.09	.913
	M	3.14		
	T	3.16		

Notes: **p<0.01, ***p<0.001; JL= Job level, J= Junior Management (N=81), M=Middle Management (N=91), T=Top Management (N=38).

The results of ANOVA for the differences in perceptions towards HCVR by tenure in the firm are shown in Table 4. The analysis showed significant differences in perceptions in 4 items. For the items “HC should be valued and reported” and “HC should be considered as an asset,”

respondents with longer tenure in the firm scored higher and significantly different from the other two categories. For the item “HCVR will influence a firm’s capability to attract and retain employees,” respondents with 5 to 10 years tenure in the firm significantly differ from respondents having less than 5 years tenure in the firm. For the item “HCVR will create competitive advantage,” respondents with less than 5 years tenure in the firm scored lower and significantly different from the other two categories.

Table 3: Perceptions towards HCVR by Tenure

	T	Mean	F	Sig.
Awareness of the concept of HCVR	>10	3.77	1.43	.240
	5-10	3.80		
	<5	3.58		
HC should be valued and reported	>10	4.90	4.28	.015*
	5-10	4.60		
	<5	4.59		
HC should be considered as an asset	>10	2.48	4.28	.015*
	5-10	2.14		
	<5	2.10		
Firms should make arrangements to value HC	>10	3.96	1.03	.358
	5-10	3.93		
	<5	3.71		
Firms should make arrangements to report HCV information in annual reports	>10	2.32	.08	.922
	5-10	2.20		
	<5	2.23		
HCVR will influence a firm’s capability to attract and retain employees	>10	4.19	6.99	.001**
	5-10	4.27		
	<5	3.77		
HCVR will enhance job satisfaction	>10	3.93	.31	.728
	5-10	4.08		
	<5	4.04		
HCVR will enhance career satisfaction	>10	4.32	1.31	.272
	5-10	4.24		
	<5	4.09		
HCVR will create transparency	>10	3.74	1.19	.306
	5-10	3.44		
	<5	3.51		
HCVR will create a standard	>10	3.77	.98	.376
	5-10	3.52		
	<5	3.59		
HCVR will create a competitive advantage	>10	3.96	7.57	.001**
	5-10	3.80		
	<5	3.38		
HCVR will hinder interpersonal relationships	>10	3.16	.09	.913
	5-10	3.14		
	<5	3.00		

Notes: * p<0.05, **p<0.01; T=Tenure, >10=Over 10 years (N=31), 5-10=Between 5 to 10 years (N=87), <5=Less than 5 years (N=92).

5 CONCLUSION

The need to meet the increasing business opportunities of the future, and simultaneously maintaining or improve the current level of performance, has made organizations look consciously into human resources as the future leverage for success. The findings of the study imply the need to adopt a 'prudent and comprehensive disclosure policy'. Valuing and reporting of human resources proves the fact that people are “felt wanted” and builds a “state

of ownership” in the employees. Employees feel that recognizing them in the form of a valuing strategy would lead to increasing a firm’s capability to attract and retain employees, and enhance employees’ career and job satisfaction.

Though initiatives on HCVR call for more information to be included in firms’ annual reports, there is no one universal formula or single set of figures that can be reported. The organizations have to tailor a common framework for external reporting that suits their own specific industry, goals, and environment. This will need to include key measures of the value which people add to the firm, such as productivity and profit per full time employee; investments in learning and development and performance management systems; rewards distribution and progression through the organization; human capital utilization such as labor turnover rates, and recruitment costs; and key employee statistics in areas such as employee attitudes and demographic composition.

As an exploratory study, the research was limited to a small sample of 210 respondents from the service industry. Further, as an exploratory study, the research neither applied existing HCVR frameworks in the Sri Lankan context nor proposed such a framework for the Sri Lankan context. Future research could look into the possibilities of applying Western HCVR frameworks in the Sri Lankan context and also propose new frameworks to suit the Sri Lankan context.

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